

Action of Thioureas as Corrosion Inhibitors for 3S Aluminium in Hydrochloric Acid Solution

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Inhibitive power of thiourea N-allyl thiourea, Phenyl thiourea, N-N Diethyl thiourea and 1:3 Di-o-tolyl thiourea for the corrosion of 3S aluminium by hydrochloric acid solution has been studied.

All the compounds studied in the present investigation are excellent corrosion inhibitors, the percentage efficiency being in the following order with respect to their highest concentrations.

N-Allylthiourea > Phenyl thiourea > Thiourea \approx N-N Diethyl thiourea > 1:3 Di-o-tolyl thiourea.

Polarization studies reveal that cathodic polarization is more pronounced than anodic polarization.

THE corrosion of aluminium and its alloys by hydrochloric acid solutions has been studied previously¹⁻⁶. Extensive corrosion problems are encountered in chemical industries where aluminium vessels are used for handling acidic solution. Thiourea has been studied as corrosion inhibitor for aluminium and its alloys in hydrochloric acid solution⁷⁻⁹, although in the present investigation results of thioureas have been given only for comparison.

In the present work an attempt has been made to evaluate the inhibitive power of thiourea, phenyl thiourea, N-allyl thiourea, N-N-Diethyl thiourea and 1:3 Di-o-tolyl thiourea towards 3S aluminium (98% Al) in 0.5N hydrochloric acid solution.

Experimental

The aluminium sheet (S.W.G. 22, 1/2 hard) used had following composition. Al—98, Cu—0.15, Mn—1.0, Fe—0.75 and Si—0.6% (maximum). Rectangular specimens of size 3×6 cm were used. Preparation, testing and cleaning procedures adopted as described by Champion⁷. Each specimen was fully immersed in 250 ml of 0.5N hydrochloric acid solution. Results of the inhibitive power of the compounds are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1. WEIGHT LOSS DATA. 3S ALUMINIUM IN 0.5N HYDROCHLORIC ACID SOLUTION IN PRESENCE OF 0.02% THIOUREAS

Size : 3 × 6 cm Temperature : 30° ± 2° Duration : 1 day

Name of the inhibitor	Loss (mg)	Inhibition (%)
Blank	1125	—
Thiourea	138	88
N-Allyl thiourea	48	96
N-N-Diethylthiourea	78	93
1:3 Di-o-tolylthiourea	114	90
Phenyl thiourea	58	94

For the galvanostatic studies, the coupons used had an effective area of 4 sq. cm (2×2 cm), the length of the handle being 4 cm. The handle, as well as the back of the test coupons and auxiliary platinum electrode, were coated with perspex and wax. Experiments were carried out in 100 ml. of Corning brand beakers at 30° ± 2°. The polarization studies have been carried out as described by Gatos⁸. The concentration of inhibitor selected was that at which maximum protection was observed. The current density was varied from 2.5 mA to 50 mA/sq. cm. The results of polarization studies have been represented in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Effect of current density on the cathode and anode potential of 3S aluminium in uninhibited 0.5N hydrochloric acid solution.

Fig. 2. Effect of current density on the cathode and anode potential of 3S aluminium in 0.5N hydrochloric acid solution with

- AA'—0.02% Phenyl thiourea
 BB'—0.02% N-Allyl thiourea
 CC'—0.02% N-N-Diethyl thiourea
 DD'—0.02% Di-o-Tolyl thiourea.

Results and Discussion

The order of increasing inhibitive power is as follows :

N-Allylthiourea > Phenyl thiourea > Thiourea > N-N Diethyl thiourea > 1 : 3 Di-o-tolyl thiourea.

Urea has practically little inhibitive power towards 3S aluminium in 0.5N hydrochloric acid. Substitution of oxygen by sulphur increases the inhibitive power tremendously⁹. This reveals that the inhibitive power is due to adsorption of the thiourea to the metal through sulphur atoms. Amongst the substituted thioureas, only N-allyl thiourea and phenyl thiourea show some increase in the inhibitive power while the rest of the substituted compounds show no improvement. Thus, substitution at one of the nitrogen atoms favours the increase while the symmetrical substitution at both the nitrogen atoms does not favour the increase of the inhibition.

The increase in adsorption on substitution of organic groups can be considered in the light of change of electronic structure of substituted groups and structure of adsorbed film.

It is well known that phenyl group is electrophilic and alkyl group is nucleophilic. In the case of

N-allyl thiourea electron density on nitrogen atom increases, hence it is very effective in inhibitive power; while phenyl thiourea is less effective because phenyl group decreases electron density on nitrogen atom. The adsorbed molecules may be considered to be covered by it while rotating around the area covered will depend on the mode of adsorption and the length of the chain.

Polarization data reveal that the cathode is more polarized than the anode. High polarization of the cathodes at low current densities indicate film formation at the cathodic sites. The Tafel equation is obeyed for the plot of cathodic polarization vs. logarithm of current density. By extrapolating the cathodic polarization line in the absence and presence of the inhibitors, the current density can be calculated and by applying the following equation one can calculate the percentage inhibition.

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = \frac{I_0 - I_w}{I_0} \times 100$$

where I_0 = corrosion current without inhibitor, and I_w = corrosion current with inhibitor.

The values of Tafel parameters and the percentage efficiency of the inhibitors in 0.5N hydrochloric acid evaluated by extrapolating the cathodic polarization line to the open circuit potential are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2. TAFEL PARAMETERS

Temperature : $30 \pm 2^\circ$

Solution	Tafel slope cathodic	Corrosion current from extrapolation of cathodic Tafel line A/Cm ²	% Inhibitor Efficiencies	
			From extrapolation of cathodic Tafel line	From loss in weight method
0.5N HCl	0.33	1.00×10^{-3}	—	—
0.5N HCl + 0.02% Phenyl thiourea	0.16	4.47×10^{-5}	96	93-94
0.5N HCl + 0.02% N-Allyl thiourea	0.15	1.45×10^{-5}	99	91-96
0.5N HCl + 0.02% N-N-Diethylthiourea	0.18	8.92×10^{-6}	99	90-93
0.5N HCl + 0.02% 1 : 3-Di-o-Tolyl-thiourea	0.14	1.12×10^{-6}	99	87-90

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